

CEDEFOP

European Centre for the Development
of Vocational Training

European Vocational Teacher Survey

Supporting VET teachers' professional development

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Giving voice to 14000 IVET teachers in 23 European countries

**Drivers & barriers
to CPD participation**

**VET teachers'
CPD needs**

**CPD effectiveness
on job performance**

EVTS campaign #MoreThanTeaching

What is the EVTS?

The European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS) is an important social survey conducted on behalf of Cedefop, and EU agency. The EVTS is Europe's first major survey dedicated to understanding the skill gaps, professional development and working conditions of teachers in vocational education and training (VET) schools.

How does it work?

Who can participate?

Randomly selected teachers who teach vocational or general education subjects for students at initial VET schools.

How?

You will receive an invitation email with a number and password to log in and complete the survey.

When?

You can participate between October 2025 and June 2026.

How long does it take?

It takes 30 minutes to complete the online survey.

Why participate?

Influence policy

Your responses will help inform better national and European policies for the teaching profession in VET that will, among others, prepare VET teachers for major social challenges, such as AI, climate change and social exclusion.

Engagement opportunities

Gain exclusive access to online events, network with other teachers, and share best practices.

Recognition

Receive a personalized certificate of participation from Cedefop.

Monetary incentives

To reward participating schools, we additionally offer vouchers for schools to buy equipment.

Make your voice heard!

By taking part, you contribute to **vital research** that will benefit teachers

Contact Information?

For more information, visit the EVTS website at <https://www.evts2025.eu>

Who is conducting the research?

The European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training (Cedefop) is an EU agency that supports the promotion, development and implementation of the Union policy in the field of vocational education and training (VET) as well as skills and qualifications policies by working together with the European Commission, Member States and social partners.

The survey is carried with the support of Verian (Verian Group Belgium SA) - an independent research, evidence, evaluation, and communications agency.

Welcome, VET Teachers to the European Vocational Teacher Survey!

[Click here to login and complete the survey](#)

Your participation in the European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS) is critical to improving vocational education and training across Europe. This section provides all the information you need to contribute effectively and understand the impact of your involvement.

Why Participate?

As a VET teacher, your insights are invaluable. Your responses, along with those of thousands of VET teachers across the EU, will provide valuable evidence to improve policies aimed at enhancing the effectiveness of continuing professional development (CPD) of teachers in initial VET schools within EU Members States. The survey results will inform strategies aimed at enhancing professional development opportunities, improving teaching practices, and supporting your growth as an educator.

> **Influence policy:** Your responses will contribute to the development of national and European policies that support the continuing professional development of VET teachers. [Read more...](#)

Join us in EVTS official launch

 | **CEDEFOP** | European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training

SHAPING LEARNING AND SKILLS FOR EUROPE

Fourth Policy learning forum

Launching the European Vocational Teacher Survey (EVTS)

25-26 September 2025

Hybrid event

#VETTeachersTrainers
#VETtoolkit

If your school has been chosen to be part of this initiative

Participate in the EVTS
to voice what works—
and what can be improved!

#MoreThanTeaching

 EVTS EUROPEAN VOCATIONAL TEACHER SURVEY

Thank you

www.cedefop.europa.eu

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